

**Three new and some rare weevils in Hungary
(Coleoptera: Curculionidae)**

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Abstract – Three weevil species (Coleoptera: Curculionidae), namely *Brachysomus verae* Košťál, 1992, *Otiorhynchus aurifer* Boheman, 1842, and *Otiorhynchus turca* Boheman, 1842, are reported from Hungary for the first time. According to recent taxonomic changes, *Otiorhynchus rotundus* Marseul, 1872 is deleted from the Hungarian checklist as its data pertain to *Otiorhynchus smreczynskii* Cmoluch, 1968. Recent records of *Ceutorhynchus subpilosus* C. N. F. Brisout de Barneville, 1881, *Curculio gyongyiae* Szénási, 2022, *Mogulones albolineatus* (J. Frivaldszky, 1878), *Otiorhynchus juglandis* Apfelbeck, 1895, and *Otiorhynchus ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842 are also presented.

Key words – Palearctic Region, faunistics, new country records

INTRODUCTION

The author and his friends are involved in various conservation projects, which provide the possibility to collect and study the weevil fauna (Coleoptera: Curculionoidea) of different areas in Hungary. The present paper publishes locality data of some rare species of true weevils (Curculionidae), including three new country records; hence, raises the number of Curculionoidea of Hungary from 1231 (SZÉNÁSI 2023) to 1234 species. All specimens were identified by the author.

Abbreviations – CBS = private collection of Béla Szelenczey (Győr, Hungary), CVS = private collection of Valentin Szénási (Isaszeg, Hungary), HNHM = Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary).

SPECIES NEW TO HUNGARY

Brachysomus verae Košťál, 1992
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – **Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County:** Bököny, Érpataki-főfolyás, 14.V.2023, 21.V.2023, 1.VI.2023, leg. N. Tóth, M. Lukátsi, B. Szelenczey, V. Szénási (14 specimens in CVS, 3 specimens in HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species has been known from Romania, Slovakia, and Ukraine (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). Proposed Hungarian name: kárpáti gyepormányos.

Otiorhynchus aurifer Boheman, 1842
(Fig. 2)

Material examined – **Budapest:** District XXII, István Pógyor street, 1.VIII.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi (1 specimen in CVS).

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species occurs mainly in Southern Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023); however, in the recent years it has been expanding, mainly in human environments (personal observation). Proposed Hungarian name: mediterrán gyalogormányos.

Otiorhynchus turca Boheman, 1842
(Fig. 3)

Material examined – **Győr-Moson-Sopron County:** Győr, Bécsi kapu square, from *Prunus laurocerasus* L. (Rosaceae), 9.VII.2024, leg. B. Szelenczey (1 specimen in CBS, 1 specimen in CVS); Győr, Bercsényi-liget, from *Prunus laurocerasus*, 11.VIII.2024, leg. B. Szelenczey (4 specimens in CBS, 3 specimens in CVS, 2 specimens in HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species occurs in the Mediterranean Region, Asia Minor, and the Caucasus (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023); however, in the recent years it has been expanding, mainly in human environments (personal observation). Proposed Hungarian name: török gyalogormányos.

Figs 1–3. 1 = *Brachysomus verae* Košťál, 1992, 2 = *Otiorhynchus aurifer* Boheman, 1842, 3 = *Otiorhynchus turca* Boheman, 1842. Not to scale (photos by Aranka Grabant (Fig. 1) and Valentin Szénási (Figs 2–3))

NEW RECORDS OF RARE OR EXPANDING SPECIES

Ceutorhynchus subpilosus C. N. F. Brisout de Barneville, 1881

Material examined – **Komárom-Esztergom County:** Lábatlan, Nagy-Pisznice, 14.XI.2023, 29.XII.2023, leg. A. Kotán, T. Németh, V. Szénási (4 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM).

Remarks – Since its first record from Hungary (MERKL *et al.* 2012) no further specimens have been reported from the country. The species occurs in Europe and the Caucasus (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023).

Curculio gyongyiae Szénási, 2022

Material examined – **Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County:** Cserépfalu, Mész hill, 19.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási, D. Saláta (3 specimens in CVS); **Fejér County:** Pákozd, Nagy-Mező, 21.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS); **Heves County:** Eger, Kis-Eged, 19.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási, D. Saláta (3 specimens in CVS); Hatvan, Kiszombos, wood pasture, 19.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási, D. Saláta

(2 specimens in CVS); **Pest County:** Galgamácsa, Ördög-árok, 3.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS); Perbál, Meszesek, 16.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Püspökhatvan, Majóka, 18.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); **Vas County:** Kenyeri, Királykút, 11.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS).

Remarks – The species is known from Croatia, Greece, and Hungary (SZÉNÁSI 2022).

Mogulones albolineatus (J. Frivaldszky, 1878)

Material examined – **Bács-Kiskun County:** Bugac, Borókás, from *Onosma arenaria* Waldst. et Kit. (Boraginaceae), 1.XI.2024, leg. V. Szénási, A. Kotán, B. Szelenczey (2 specimens in CVS).

Remarks – The taxonomic status of this species was recently clarified (KRÁTKÝ *et al.* 2018). So far it has been recorded from Bulgaria, Hungary, Iran, Russia, Slovakia, and Turkey, but the available data on its distribution are evidently far from complete (KRÁTKÝ *et al.* 2018). It is apparently very rare in Hungary.

Otiorhynchus ovalipennis Boheman, 1842

Material examined – **Budapest:** District XI, Kelenhegyi street, on the wall, 5.VII.2023, leg. T. Németh (1 specimen in CVS); **Pest County:** Isaszeg, Batthyány street, from *Prunus laurocerasus*, 24–27.VIII.2023, 7.IX.2023, leg. V. Szénási (7 specimens in CVS, 2 specimens in HNHM); Veresegyház, Zoltán Kodály street, from *Prunus laurocerasus*, 28.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS).

Remarks – The species occurs in Southern Europe, the Middle East, and the Caucasus (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). It was found in Hungary in 2023 (SZÉNÁSI 2023) and apparently has been expanding, mainly in human environments (personal observation).

Otiorhynchus smreczynskii Cmoluch, 1968

Material examined – **Budapest:** District XXII, Kamaraerdei street 8, 4.VI.2020, 27.VIII.2023, leg. M. Lukátsi (3 specimens in CVS, 2 specimens in HNHM); **Komárom-Esztergom County:** Szomor, Szabadság square, from *Ligustrum vulgare* L. (Oleaceae), 6.IX.2023, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); **Pest County:** Budafok, Falka street, 20.IX.2021, leg. M. Lukátsi (6 specimens in CVS, 2 specimens in HNHM); Gödöllő, Röges street, from *Ligustrum vulgare*, 31.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Gödöllő, Peres street, from

Syringa vulgaris L. (Oleaceae), 28.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (6 specimens in CVS, 2 specimens in HNHM); Gödöllő, Köztársaság road, 28.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Isaszeg, Bartók Béla street 36, from *Ligustrum vulgare*, 24.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens in CVS); Isaszeg, Madách Imre street, from *Spirea media* Schmidt, 1792 (Rosaceae), 31.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Piliscsaba, industrial area, from *Syringa vulgaris*, 30.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens in CVS); Pilisszántó, Pilistető, from *Ligustrum vulgare* and *Prunus spinosa* L. (Rosaceae), 8.IX.2023, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in HNHM, 2 specimens in CVS); Szada, Székely Bertalan street, from *Syringa vulgaris*, 28.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); Törökbálint, Nagy Pusztá, from *Ligustrum vulgare*, 19.VI.2024, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Veresegyház, Kálvin square, from *Spirea media*, 28.VIII.2023, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS); **Zala County:** Cserszegtomaj, Dobogó, 1.VIII.2023, leg. A. Márkus (4 specimens in CVS); Keszthely, Kertváros, 1.VIII.2023, leg. A. Márkus (1 specimen in CVS).

Remarks – This species is very common in the urban areas of Hungary. *Otiorhynchus rotundus* Marseul, 1872, previously included in the Hungarian checklist (PODLUSSÁNY *et al.* 2019), is to be deleted due to recent changes in the taxonomy and delineations of distributional areas of certain species (GOSIK *et al.* 2023); its records pertain to *Otiorhynchus smreczynskii* Cmoluch, 1968.

Otiorhynchus juglandis Apfelbeck, 1895

Material examined – **Pest County:** Pilisszántó, Pilistető, 8.IX.2023, leg. V. Szénási (8 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); **Veszprém County:** Tihany, at ferry, 4.VIII.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi (5 specimens in CVS).

Remarks – The species occurs in Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023); it is considered very rare in Hungary.

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Acknowledgements – I would like to thank everyone who contributed to this study, chiefly Győző Szél and Aranka Grabant (HNHM) for the possibility to review relevant parts of the collection under their care. Thanks are also due to Attila Kotán, Márk Lukátsi, András Márkus, Tamás Németh, Dénes Saláta, Béla Szelenczey, and Norbert Tóth for collecting weevils either with me or for me.

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